

Research Paper

Participation Analysis of the Indonesian Advisory Agency Communication (BKPRMI) in Musyawarah Development Planning (Musrenbang) Village in the District of Lubuk Pakam, Regency Deli Serdang

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ABSTRACT

Good development will take place if started with a good plan as well, so that it can be implemented by all development factors and meet the needs of the community. Therefore, the planning process requires the involvement of the community among youth through public consultation or Development Planning Council (Musrenbang). The Musrenbang process basically records the aspirations and needs of the community that are formulated through the discussion at the village / kelurahan level. Because only with the participation of the beneficiary community, the results of the development will be in accordance with the aspirations and needs of the community itself. The study was conducted in Kecamatan Lubuk pakam of Deli Serdang Regency on "Participation Analysis of Indonesian Mosque Youth Mosque Board (BKPRMI) in Development Planning Meeting (Musrenbang) Village in Kecamatan Lubuk Pakam Deli Serdang Regency Year 2017". The method of analysis used in this study is multiple linear regression analysis and descriptive analysis with the sample number of respondents 66 people from 195 people the population. Sampling of respondents is based on probability sampling. From the result of the research, it is found that the factors influencing the participation of Indonesian Mosque Youth Mosque Youth Board (BKPRMI) in Musrenbang, namely education, occupation, understanding, and regulation simultaneously have a significant effect. Partially, education and understanding variables have positive and significant effect on BKPRMI participation, while work and regulatory variables have positive but not significant effect on BKPRMI participation. BKPRMI participation variables that include decision making, implementation, receiving benefits, and assessing program outcomes simultaneously have a positive and significant influence on village Musrenbang. Partially, decision-making and receiving variable have positive and significant effect to village Musrenbang, while implementation variable and rate of program result have positive but not significant influence to village Musrenbang.

Keywords: BKPRMI Participation, Village Musrenbang

INTRODUCTION

Indonesia is one of the developing countries in the world that has great duties and responsibilities in realizing national aspirations and mandates as set out in the 1945 Constitution. The constitutional mandate requires an equitable improvement in people's welfare. The role of government

is considered important because the government becomes a "development agent" or a driving force for renewal / development (Abraham in Tjokroamidjojo, 1990: 18). Therefore, development is important in order to realize a better and more equitable improvement in community welfare. Development carried out by the government

cannot run well if it is not accompanied by regional development. Regional development is an integral part of national development. For this reason, the implementation of the Indonesian state government must prioritize the principle of decentralization in focusing on democracy.

Development as a process of increasing human ability to determine its future means that the community needs to be involved in the process (Bryant and White, 1987: 268). Pelu people take part in answering the problems that occur. Nurcholis, et al. (2009: 11) suggest that the involvement of the community (Stakeholders) is very important because basically the main actors of development in the regional autonomy system are the community. The involvement of youth in development is needed starting from the development planning process itself. Containers to implement this are often called the Development Planning Consultation or Musrenbang which is a forum between actors in the framework of preparing national development plans and regional development plans (Sutrisno in Pramusinto, 2009: 166).

Youth participation in development, especially in the development planning process can be seen in the presence of youth in the village / kelurahan Musrenbang forum. The willingness of the youth to attend the village / kelurahan Musrenbang can be said to be a manifestation of youth's concern for the progress of development in their area. The youth's presence in the village / kelurahan Musrenbang is a process in which youth can submit proposals and aspirations to be involved directly in planning development programs in their area. In addition, the presence of youth as village / kelurahan Musrenbang participants implies the creation of democratic rights. This means that in the village / kelurahan Musrenbang, youth are free to express their opinions and young people are invited to dialogue for the development planning. The importance of youth participation in regional development planning has basically

been a concern of the government. The government implements Participatory Planning in development planning to capture the aspirations and involvement of youth that will be gathered into a regional development program. However, these aspirations in the next stage must be synchronized with top-down planning. Therefore, synchronization of government policies, local government policies, and youth needs are expected to be achieved through youth participation in the village Musrenbang forum or better known as bottom-up planning and top-down planning, although not all youth needs are synchronized with government policies area. This is in line with Conyers (1991: 200) that community proposals and suggestions are often not in accordance with the plans that have been made even though the suggestions and suggestions are reasonable. In planning most plans are arranged in a top-down planning manner. As a result, most of the development activities carried out are not in accordance with the aspirations and desires of the people so that the utilization of the results of development by the community becomes not optimal (Sjafrizal, 2009: 76).

Through the implementation of the village / kelurahan Musrenbang, the community can convey their aspirations in order to plan a development activity program. One of the development plans that must be prepared by regional governments is regional annual planning or called the Regional Development Work Plan (RKPD). The Regional Development Work Plan is an official regional plan document that is required to direct regional development within the next one year. RKPD bridges annual plan synchronization with strategic plans, operationalizes strategic plans in annual steps that are more concrete and measurable to ensure the achievement of a medium-term strategic plan (Nugroho, 2011: 108-109).

This study aims to explain youth participation in the Development Planning Village (Musrenbang) in Lubuk Pakam sub-

district for the preparation of the 2017 Regional Development Work Plan (RKPD) in Lubuk Pakam Sub-District. Village Development Planning Consultation (Musrenbang) is the most the beginning was carried out in the process of drafting the RKPD and was the closest point to the youth to accommodate the aspirations of youth in each village / kelurahan. The village / kelurahan community as the direct beneficiaries of development results participate in determining the types of activities to be carried out and knowing the impacts that will be caused, and the social costs that must be paid (Riyadi, 2005: 314).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Participation

Participation comes from English, "participation" is taking part or participation. Mubyarto means participation as an act of taking part in activities, while community participation itself is the involvement of the community in a development process where the community is involved starting from the stage of program preparation, planning and development, policy formulation and decision making (Huraerah, 2011: 110). In line with that, Sulaiman expressed participation as an active involvement of community members individually, in groups or in community unity in the process of joint decision making, program planning and implementation as well as service efforts and social welfare development within and or outside the community on the basis of a sense of awareness social responsibility (Huraerah, 2011: 110).

Level of Participation

The level of community participation in development is seen as one of the benchmarks for the success of development, and is a reflection that in community development it focuses more on human and community aspects, not merely on physical material. According to Keith Davis in Suciati (2006) it was stated that the forms of community participation are in the form of; a) mind, b) energy, c) expertise, d)

goods, and e) money. This form of community participation is carried out in various ways, namely; a) consultant, usually in the form of services, b) spontaneous contributions in the form of money and goods, c) establishing projects that are independent and funded by the community themselves, d) contributions in the form of work, e) mass actions, f) conducting development within the family, and g) building autonomous community projects.

Understanding Youth

According to the Youth Act number 40 of 2009, youth are those aged 16 years to 30 years. History proves that youth play an important role in independence everywhere, where the state of independence has never escaped the participation of youth. Because pemuda have enthusiasm and ambitious high in achieving their desires, fighting for, maintaining change towards a better. Youth has a lot of potential embedded in him, young people must dare to dream and aspire to the highest.

Indonesian Mosque Youth Youth Communication Agency (BKPRMI)

In the BKPRMI bylaws chapter 1 article 1, it is explained that the definition of the institution is da'wah and youth organizations. The Indonesian Mosque Youth Youth Communication Agency (BKPRMI) is an association of youth and youth mosque activists, which makes the mosque the center of aqeedah, morality, ukhuwah, scientific and skill fostering activities.

The aim of BKPRMI is to foster and develop the potential of young mosque youth who are devoted to Allah SWT. Having a complete and solid Islamic and Indonesian insight, which always prospers the mosque as a center of worship and struggle, empowers the ummah to realize the marhamah society by adhering to the principles of aqeedah, ukhuwah, and Islamic da'wah and the unitary state of the Republic of Indonesia. (Yanuar, A. et al. 1997: 3). The direction of struggle by the Indonesian Mosque Youth Youth Communication Agency (BKPRMI) is anticipated;

1) Guidance of the Ummah

BKPRMI has the attitude that all Islamic organizations are believers, aspirations and armies in realizing al-Islam. For this reason BKPRMI invites cooperation and mosque-based in building the Islamic ummah.

2) Relationships with Government and Society.

BKPRMI is one of the Indonesian youth groups. As an Indonesian citizen who has social responsibility, he actively participates in realizing the nation's development towards a just and prosperous society blessed by Allah SWT.

3) BKPRMI supports and plays an active role in creating a harmonious atmosphere, peace in the midst of society, both nationally and internationally.

The Concept of Youth Participation

Youth participation is an inseparable part of public participation. This means that in the discussion of community participation contains elements of youth participation specifically. Thus, in this discussion the study of youth participation is an integral part of the study of community participation.

Regarding community participation in this case youth, based on Law number 25 of 2004, explained that one of the national development planning systems was aimed at optimizing community participation. Furthermore, about community participation is also mentioned in articles 5, 6 and 7 of the same law. In this law development is a combination of top-down and bottom-up approaches that emphasize aspirational and participatory ways. In addition to Law number 25 of 2004, there are also other laws and regulations that emphasize the need for community participation in development planning, namely Law number 32 of 2004 concerning Regional Government and Government Regulation of the Republic of Indonesia number 8 of 2008 concerning stages, procedures, compilation, controlling and evaluating the implementation of regional development plans.

Village Development Planning Consultation (Village Musrenbang)

Good development will be carried out if it starts with good planning, so that it can be carried out by all development actors and meet the needs of the community. For this reason, the planning process requires community involvement, including through public consultations or Development Planning Consultations (Musrenbang). Musrenbang is a consultation forum for stakeholders to produce development planning agreements in the relevant regions according to their regional level. The implementation of the musrenbang includes the preparation, discussion and formulation of program / activity priorities, formulation of consensus agreements and post-Musrenbang activities. (Siagian: 1994)

Musrenbang is the main vehicle for public consultations used by the government in the preparation of national and regional development plans in Indonesia. The annual Musrenbang is a stakeholder consultation forum for annual development planning, which is carried out in stages through a "bottom-up planning" mechanism, starting from the village / kelurahan musrenbang, sub-district musrenbang, SKPD (Regional Work Unit) forum and district / city musrenbang, and for the next level the results of the kabupaten / kota musrenbang are also used as input for the provincial musrenbang.

The musrenbang process basically records the aspirations and needs of the community which are formulated through discussions at the village / kelurahan level, continued at the sub-district level, collected based on obligatory affairs and regional government choices, and then processed and prioritized at the district / city program / activity by the joint Bappeda stakeholders adjusted to funding capabilities.

At the village / kelurahan level, the function of the musrenbang is to agree on priority issues in the village / kelurahan area, programs and activities that can be funded by Village Fund Allocation (ADD), proposed to the APBD, or which will be implemented through community self-help and the Village Budget. delegates who will

attend the sub-district musrenbang. At the sub-district level, the function of the musrenbang is to agree on sub-district scale issues and issues, village / kelurahan program priorities and activities, agree on cross-village / kelurahan programs and activities in the respective sub-districts, as input for the SKPD Forum and sub-district considerations, according to their duties and his authority in preparing the District Work Plan.

MATERIALS & METHODS

This research was conducted in Lubuk Pakam District, which is one of the sub-districts in Deli Serdang Regency, North Sumatra Province. By taking research locations in five villages or villages, namely, Sekip village, Merbau III fence village, Tanjung Garbus village, Shahmad village, and Pakam village III. This research was conducted from April to June 2017. This research was conducted through a scientific approach using theoretical structures to construct one or more hypotheses that require qualitative and quantitative testing. This study was to find out the participation of the Indonesian Mosque Youth Youth Communication Board (BKPRMI) on village Development Planning Consultations (Musrenbang) in Lubuk Pakam District, Deli Serdang Regency. This type of research is hypothesis testing research that takes samples from the population and sets criteria according to the research objectives. Data needed in this study include:

1. Primary data, which is obtained through a series of questions submitted to respondents in the form of questionnaires and interviews.

2. Secondary data, obtained from relevant agencies such as the Village Office and data sourced from relevant agencies that support this research.

This study analyzed the participation of youth communication committees of Indonesian mosques (BPRMI) towards the development planning deliberation process (Musrenbang) in the sub-district of Lubuk Pakam District Deli Serdang. Therefore, the populations in this study were all members of BKPRMI who were in the sub-district of Lubuk Pakam.

Samples are part of the number and characteristics possessed by the population (Sugiyono; 2006). In sampling, you should use methods that are more scientifically accountable. In this study, the authors used random sampling or random sampling techniques.

To determine the number of respondents or samples, researchers used the Slovin formula (Prasetyo; 2005), namely:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$$

Information:

n = Sample Size

N = Population Size

e = Error Tolerance Limit 10% = 0,1. So that the number of samples obtained is:

$$n = \frac{195}{1 + 195 (0.1)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{195}{2.95}$$

$$n = 66,10$$

From 195 populations, a sample of 66 respondents was obtained. Members of the BKPRMI sub-district were taken by 18 people from the daily board and each of 10 people from 3 villages / kelurahan and each of the 9 people from the 2 villages / kelurahan.

Table 1. Research Populations and Samples

No.	Types of Populations and Samples	Population	Sampel	Percen
1	Member of District BKPRMI	36	18	27,27%
2	Member of BKPRMI Sekip Village	45	10	15,15%
3	Member of BKPRMI Pagar Merbau I Village	25	10	15,15%
4	Member of BKPRMI Pagar Merbau III Village	26	9	13,64%
5	Members of BKPRMI Pakam III Village	30	9	13,64%
6	Member of BKPRMI Syahmad Village	33	10	15,15%
	Total	195	66	100%

Source: 2017 Research Results

RESULT

General Description of the Research Area

Lubuk Pakam District is one of the sub-districts in Deli Serdang Regency, North Sumatra. Geographically, Lubuk Pakam sub-district is located at position 02 ° 57 'North Latitude - 03 ° 16' North Latitude and 98 ° 33 'East Longitude - 99 ° 27 East Longitude with a range of 0 - 500 meters above sea level, with an area reaching 31.19 Km² or 0.013% of the area of Deli Serdang Regency with 13 villages / kelurahan.

Lubuk Pakam sub-district has 13 villages / villages, and there are 5 villages / kelurahan including Sekip village, Merbau 3 fence village, Tanjung Garbus village, Shahmad village, and Pakam village 3. The

administrative area of Lubuk Pakam sub-district is limited to:

North Side : Beringin District
 South : Pagar Merbau District
 West side : Tanjung Morawa District
 East : Beringin and Pagar Merbau Districts

Testing Validity and Reliability

Validity test

Testing the validity of the instrument using statistical software, the value of validity can be seen in the Corrected Item-Total Correlation column. If the correlation number obtained is greater than the critical number ($r\text{-count} > r\text{-table}$) then the instrument is said to be valid, where the $r\text{-table}$ value for the sample is 25 respondents is 0.396, as shown below.

Table 2. Results of testing the validity of research variables

Variable	Statement Item	r-count	r-table	Information
Educational, Occupational, Understanding and regulatory factors	1	0,721	0.396	Valid
	2	0,762	0.396	Valid
	3	0,687	0.396	Valid
	4	0,787	0.396	Valid
Participation (Indonesian Mosque Youth Youth Communication Agency) BKPRMI	1	0,844	0.396	Valid
	2	0,846	0.396	Valid
	3	0,842	0.396	Valid
	4	0,827	0.396	Valid
	5	0,822	0.396	Valid
	6	0,841	0.396	Valid
	7	0,826	0.396	Valid
	8	0,837	0.396	Valid
	9	0,825	0.396	Valid
	10	0,835	0.396	Valid
	11	0,826	0.396	Valid
	12	0,832	0.396	Valid
Village Development Planning Consultation Process (MUSRENBANG)	1	0,729	0.396	Valid
	2	0,722	0.396	Valid
	3	0,779	0.396	Valid
	4	0,744	0.396	Valid
	5	0,763	0.396	Valid
	6	0,772	0.396	Valid
	7	0,738	0.396	Valid
	8	0,729	0.396	Valid
	9	0,699	0.396	Valid
	10	0,728	0.396	Valid

Source: Results of 2017 Primary Data Processing

Based on the results of the validity test, it can be concluded that all the statement items to measure each research variable are declared valid. It can be seen that the $r\text{-count}$ is greater than $r\text{-table}$.

Reliability Test

Reliability testing is done to show the extent to which a measuring device can be trusted. In general, an instrument is said to be good if it has an alpha Cronbach's coefficient > 0.6 so that the research questionnaire is declared reliable.

Table 3. Reliability Test Results

Variable	Alpha Cronbach's	Limitation of Reliability	Information
Faktor-faktor	0.795	0,6	Reliable
Partisipasi BKPRMI	0.846	0,6	Reliable
Village Musrenbang	0.761	0,6	Reliable

Source: Results of 2017 Primary Data Processing

The test results show that the Cronbach's alpha value is >0.6 . This shows that the research data is declared reliable.

Testing of Classical Assumptions

Normality test

The data normality test aims to find out whether in the regression model the intruder or residual variable has a normal distribution. To test whether the data of this study are normally distributed or cannot be identified through 2 methods, namely graph analysis and statistical analysis

An easy way to see residual normality is to look at a probability plot that compares the cumulative distribution of a normal distribution. The normal distribution will form a diagonal straight line and plotting the residual data will be compared with the diagonal line. In addition to see residual normality, it can also be done by looking at a histogram graph that compares the observations with normal distributions that are close to the normal distribution.

By looking at the normal plot graph in Figure 4.2. it can be concluded that the data spreads around the diagonal line and follows the direction of the diagonal line. This shows that the residual data is normally distributed. Similarly, the results of the histogram graph in Figure 4.3. which shows that the residual data is normally distributed as seen from the almost perfect (symmetrical) bell-shaped image.

Statistical tests that can be used to test residual normality include the non-parametric statistical test Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S). The K-S test is done by making a hypothesis:

H_0 : Residual data is normally distributed

H_a : Residual data is not normally distributed

To determine it, the criteria are:

H_0 is accepted if the significance value (Asymp.Sig) > 0.05

H_a is accepted if the significance value (Asymp.Sig) < 0.05

Normal P-P Plot of Regression Standardized Residual

Figure 1. Normal P-Plot of Regression Standardized Residual

Figure 2. BKPRMI Participation Histogram

		Unstandardized Residual
N		66
Normal Parameters ^a	Mean	.0000000
	Std. Deviation	3.66528372
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.106
	Positive	.106
	Negative	-.062
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		.864
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.445

a. Test distribution is Normal

From the results of the statistical test in Table 4.3. shows that the Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z value is 0.864 and its significance is at 0.445 and the value is above $\alpha = 0.05$ (Asymp.Sig = 0.445 > 0.05) so that the hypothesis H_0 is accepted which means the residual data is normally distributed.

Multicollinearity Test

Multicollinearity test was conducted to test whether the regression model found a correlation between independent variables. If there is a correlation, then there is a problem called Multicollinearity. A good regression model should not have a correlation between independent variables.

Testing for the presence or absence of multicollinearity symptoms is done by considering the value of the correlation matrix produced during data processing and the value of VIF (Variance Inflation Factor) and Tolerance. VIF values of less than 10

and tolerance of more than 0.10 indicate that there are no symptoms of multicollinearity. So it can be concluded that the regression model does not have multicollinearity problems.

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	38.500	1.629		23.630	.000	
	Pendidikan	1.217	.720	.329	1.689	.096	.412
	Pekerjaan	-1.036	.814	-.266	-1.273	.208	.358
	Pemahaman	-.204	.744	-.055	-.274	.785	.388
	Peraturan daerah	.294	.756	.065	.389	.698	.568

a. Dependent Variable: Participation BKPRMI

From the calculation using the SPSS program, it can be seen that the VIF and tolerance values are as follows: Educational variables have a VIF value of 2.427 and tolerance of 0.412. Job variable has a VIF value of 2.578 and tolerance is 0.388. The understanding variable has a VIF value of 1.760 and tolerance of 0.568.

From the existing provisions that if the VIF value <10 and tolerance > 0.10 then there is no symptom of multicollinearity and the value obtained from the calculation is in accordance with the provisions of the VIF value and tolerance, and from the above analysis results can be seen the tolerance value of all independent variables (education, work, understanding and local regulations) more than 0.10 and VIF values less than 10, it can be concluded that the independent variables do not occur multicollinearity so that the model has met the requirements of classical assumptions in regression analysis.

Heteroscedasticity test

Heteroscedasticity test aims to test whether the regression model occurs inequalities of residual variance from one observation to another observation. To detect the presence or absence of heteroscedasticity can be done by looking at the graph of scatterplots. From the scatterplots graph in Figure 4.4 shows that the points spread randomly and spread both above and below the number 0 on the Y axis and do not form a regular pattern, it can be

concluded that there is no heteroscedasticity in the regression model.

Figure 3. BKPRMI scatterplots participation chart

So it can be concluded as a whole that the regression model meets the classical assumption test requirements.

Hypothesis testing

Determination Coefficient Test Results (R²)

The coefficient of determination is used to test the goodness-fit of the regression model that can be seen from the value of R Square. To find out community participation caused by several factors including education, employment, and understanding can be seen through the magnitude of the coefficient of determination.

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.834 ^a	.696	.683	2,44484

a. Predictors: (Constant), Regional regulations, education, understanding, employment
b. Dependent Variable: BKPRMI's participation

From the calculation of the value of R Square is 0.696. This means that 69.6 percent of BKPRMI participation can be explained by the four independent variables above, while the remaining 31.4 percent are explained by other causes.

Simultaneous Test Results (Test F)

The simultaneous influence test is used to determine whether the independent variables simultaneously or simultaneously affect the dependent variable. For more details, see Table 6.

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1287,311	4	321,828	53,842	,000 ^a
	Residual	561,860	94	5,977		
	Total	1849,172	98			

Simultaneous statistical tests are indicated by a comparison of the values of F calculated with F table. F table value with a confidence degree of 95 percent is 2.46. In Table 4.6 above, it can be seen that in the equation, F count 53.842 is greater than the F table. The probability level is 0,000, so it can be concluded, $P = 0,000 < \alpha = 0.05$, which means H_a is accepted. This means that the three independent variables have a

significant effect in explaining BKPRMI participation.

Partial Test Results (t-Test)

In a partial statistical test with a critical t value (critical value) at $df = (n-k)$, where n is the number of samples and k is the number of independent variables including constants. To test the coefficients of individual partial regression of each independent variable can be seen in Table 7.

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	26,610	,790		33,664	,000
	Education	1,572	,404	,363	3,889	,000
	Work	,468	,416	,111	1,127	,263
	Understanding	1,733	,426	,380	4,065	,000
	Regulations	,664	,401	,130	1,655	,101

a. Dependent Variable: BKPRMI's participation

In Table 7 above, the statistical test t is obtained, as follows:

1. Educational Variables: t-count = 3.889; t-table 1.990, with a probability level of 0.000. Thus it can be concluded $P = 0,000 < \alpha = 0.05$, reject the hypothesis H_0 and accept the H_a hypothesis which states education has a significant positive effect on BKPRMI participation.
2. Job variables: t-count = 1,127; t-table 1.990, with a probability level of 0.263. Thus it can be concluded that $P = 0.263 > \alpha = 0.05$, reject the H_a hypothesis and accept the hypothesis H_0 which states that the work does not significantly influence public participation.
3. Understanding variables: t-count = 4.065; t-table 1.990, with a probability level of 0.000. Thus it can be concluded that $P = 0,000 < \alpha = 0.05$, reject the hypothesis H_0 and accept the H_a hypothesis which states

that understanding has a significant positive effect on public participation.

4. Regulatory Variables: t-count = 1.655; t-table 1.990, with a probability level of 0.101. Thus it can be concluded $P = 0.101 > \alpha = 0.05$, reject the H_a hypothesis and accept the hypothesis H_0 which states that regional regulations have no significant effect on public participation.

Based on Table 7 and the description above, thus the multiple regression equation can be arranged as follows:

$$Y = 26,610 + 1,572 X_1 + 0,468 X_2 + 1,733 X_3 + 0,664 X_4$$

Effects of BKPRMI's Participation on the Musrenbang Process

Testing of Classical Assumptions

Normality test

The data normality test aims to find out whether in the regression model the intruder or residual variable has a normal

distribution. To test whether this research data is normally distributed or not known through 2 ways, namely graph analysis and statistical analysis.

An easy way to see residual normality is to look at a probability plot that compares the cumulative distribution of a normal distribution. The normal distribution will form a diagonal straight line and plotting the residual data will be compared with the diagonal line. In addition to see residual normality, it can also be done by looking at a histogram graph that compares the observations with normal distributions that are close to the normal distribution.

Normal P-P Plot of Regression Standardized Residual

Figure 4. Normal P-Plot of Regression Standardized

Figure 5. Histogram of the Village Musrenbang

By looking at the normal plot graph in Figure 4.5, it can be concluded that the data spreads around the diagonal line and follows the direction of the diagonal line. This shows that the residual data is normally distributed. Similarly, the results of the

histogram graph in Figure 5, which shows that the residual data is normally distributed as seen from the almost perfect (symmetrical) bell-shaped image.

Statistical tests that can be used to test residual normality include the non-parametric statistical test Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S). The K-S test is done by making a hypothesis:

Ho: Residual data is normally distributed

Ha: Residual data is not normally distributed

To determine it, the criteria are:

Ho is accepted if the significance value (Asymp.Sig) > 0.05

Ha is accepted if the significance value (Asymp.Sig) < 0.05

Table 8. Kolmogorov – Smirnov Test

		Unstandardized Residual
N		66
Normal Parameters(a,b)	Mean	,0000000
	Std. Deviation	1,95074758
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	,083
	Positive	,049
	Negative	-,083
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		,827
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		,501

a Test distribution is Normal.

b Calculated from data.

From the results of the statistical test in Table 8 shows that the Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z value is 0.827 and its significance is 0.501 and the value is above $\alpha = 0.05$ (Asymp.Sig = 0.501 > 0.05) so that the hypothesis Ho is accepted which means the residual data is distributed normal.

Multicollinearity Test

Multicollinearity test was conducted to test whether the regression model found a correlation between independent variables. If there is a correlation, then there is a problem called Multicollinearity. A good regression model should not have a correlation between independent variables. Testing for the presence or absence of multicollinearity symptoms is done by considering the value of the correlation matrix produced during data processing and the value of VIF (Variance Inflation Factor) and Tolerance. VIF values of less than 10 and tolerance of more than 0.10 indicate that

there are no symptoms of multicollinearity. So it can be concluded that the regression model does not have multicollinearity problems.

Table 9. Multicollinearity Test Results

Model		Collinearity Statistics	
		Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)		
	Decision-making	,637	1,570
	Implementation	,311	3,217
	Benefit	,378	2,646
	Assess program results	,433	2,307

a Dependent Variable: Village Musrenbang

From the calculation using the SPSS program, it can be seen that the VIF and tolerance values are as follows: The decision-making variable has a VIF value of 1.570 and tolerance is 0.637. The implementation program development variable has a VIF value of 3,217 and tolerance is 0,311. The variable receiving the benefits of a development program has a VIF value of 2.646 and tolerance of 0.378. Variables assess program results have a VIF value of 2.307 and tolerance of 0.433.

From the existing provisions that if the VIF value <10 and tolerance >0.10 then there is no symptom of multicollinearity and values obtained from the calculation are in accordance with the provisions of VIF and tolerance values, and from the above analysis results can be seen the tolerance value of all independent variables (retrieval decisions, implementation of development programs, receiving benefits, and evaluating program results) more than 0.10 and VIF values less than 10, it can be concluded that the independent variables do not occur multicollinearity so that the model meets the requirements of the classical assumptions in regression analysis.

Heteroscedasticity test

Heteroscedasticity test aims to test whether the regression model occurs inequalities of residual variance from one observation to another observation. To detect the presence or absence of heteroscedasticity can be done by looking at the graph of scatterplots.

From the scatterplots graph in Figure 4.7 shows that the points spread randomly and

spread both above and below the number 0 on the Y axis and do not form a regular pattern, it can be concluded that there is no heteroscedasticity in the regression model.

Figure 6. Graph of village Musrenbang scatterplots

So it can be concluded as a whole that the regression model meets the classical assumption test requirements.

Hypothesis testing

Determination Coefficient Test Results (R²)

The coefficient of determination is used to test the goodness-fit of the regression model that can be seen from the value of R Square. To find out community participation caused by several factors including decision making, implementation, receiving the benefits of development and assessing development outcomes can be seen through the magnitude of the coefficient determination.

Table 10. Coefficient determination.

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	,606 ^a	,368	,341	1,99182

a. Predictors: (Constant), Assess, Receive Benefits, Decisions, Implementation

b. Dependent Variable: Village Musrenbang

From the calculation of the value of R Square is 0.368. This means that 36.8 percent of Musrenbang can be explained by the four independent variables above, while the remaining 63.2 percent is explained by other influences.

Simultaneous Test Results (Test F)

The simultaneous influence test is used to determine whether the independent variables simultaneously or simultaneously

affect the dependent variable. For more details, see Table 11.

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	216,706	4	54,176	13,656	,000(a)
	Residual	372,931	94	3,967		
	Total	589,636	98			
a. Predictors:(Constant), Assess, Decision, Benefits, Implementation						
b. Dependent Variable: Village Musrenbang						

Simultaneous statistical tests are indicated by a comparison of the values of F calculated with F Table. The F Table value with a confidence degree of 95 percent is 2.46. In Table 4.11 above it can be seen that in the equation, F count 13.656 is greater than the F table. 0,000 probability level. Then it can be concluded, $P = 0,000 < \alpha = 0.05$, which means H_a is accepted. This means that all four independent variables

are simultaneously significant in explaining the Musrenbang Village.

Partial Test Results (t-Test)

In a partial statistical test with a critical t value (critical value) at $df = (n-k)$, where n is the number of samples and k is the number of independent variables including constants. To test the coefficient of individual partial regression of each independent variable can be seen in Table 12.

Table 12. T-Statistic Test

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	21,600	2,115		10,213	,000
	Decision-making	,839	,233	,370	3,598	,001
	Implementation	,129	,303	,063	,425	,672
	Benefit	,504	,248	,271	2,030	,045
	Rate	,014	,189	,009	,075	,941

a Dependent Variable: Village Musrenbang

In Table 4.12 the statistical test t is obtained, as follows:

1. Decision-making variables: t-count = 3,598; t-Table 1.990, with a probability level of 0.001. Thus it can be concluded that $P = 0.001 < \alpha = 0.05$, then reject the hypothesis H_0 and accept the H_a hypothesis which states that the decision-making variable has a significant positive effect on the Musrenbang Village.
2. Variable implementation of the development program: t-count = 0.425; t-Table 1.990, with a probability level of 0.672. Thus it can be concluded $P = 0.672 > \alpha = 0.05$, then accept the H_0 hypothesis and reject the H_a hypothesis which states that the variable implementation of the development program has no significant effect on the Musrenbang Village.

3. Variables receive the benefits of the development program: t-count = 2.030; t-Table 1.990, with a probability level of 0.045. Thus it can be concluded $P = 0.045 < \alpha = 0.05$, then reject the hypothesis H_0 and accept the H_a hypothesis which states that the variable receiving the benefits of the development program has a significant positive effect on the Musrenbang Village.
4. Variables assess the results of the development program: t-count = 0.075; t-Table 1.990, with a probability level of 0.941. Thus it can be concluded $P = 0.941 > \alpha = 0.05$, then accept the H_0 hypothesis and reject the H_a hypothesis which states that the variable assessing the results of the development program does not significantly influence the Musrenbang Village.

Based on Table 12 and the description above, thus the multiple regression equation can be arranged as follows:

$$Y = 21,600 + 0,839 X_1 + 0,129 X_2 + 0,504 X_3 + 0,014 X_4$$

DISCUSSION

Factors Affecting BKPRMI's Participation in the Musrenbang Village Process

Educational factors have a positive and significant effect on BKPRMI participation. Where the education factor has a direct influence, which means that every addition or increase in the value of one unit of education variable scores. This is estimated by the increasing education of members of BKPRMI, which will also increase with regard to various matters including the Musrenbang Village. With the increasing knowledge of BKPRMI members about the Musrenbang Village, their participation in the Musrenbang Village business tends to increase. In addition to the educational factors that influenced BKPRMI's participation in the Musrenbang process, work factors had a positive effect but did not significantly affect BKPRMI's participation. The non-effect of work factors on BKPRMI's participation was due to the lack of involvement of civil servants / ABRI in the activities carried out by the village government. According to Plumer in Suryawan (2004), community work is usually people with a certain level of work will be able to spend more or not even spend the time to participate in a particular project, often the basic reason for society is the conflict between commitment to work and the desire to participate.

Understanding factors have a positive and significant effect on BKPRMI participation. This means that the more intensive the understanding given by the village apparatus, the greater the participation of BKPRMI in the Musrenbang Village. This understanding also relates to the level of education and knowledge of the community towards youth participation in the Musrenbang Village, so

that these two factors work together, meaning that the young people's knowledge about the participation of the Musrenbang Village will be higher if the intensity of understanding given to the community is intensified. The success of the Musrenbang Village is very much determined by the level of the youth of the community and its level of youth will be expected to exist if the youth has known about their rights and obligations towards the Musrenbang Village itself. Youth who do not know their rights and obligations will find it difficult to demand and expect their participation. Regulatory factors have a positive effect but do not significantly affect BKPRMI's participation. The non-influence of regulations on BKPRMI's participation was caused by the regulations made by the village government in inviting youth to participate in musyawarah activities in village development not binding, so that the youth did not feel that it was an obligation to attend.

Effects of BKPRMI Participation on Musrenbang Village

Decision making from BKPRMI's participation has a positive and significant effect on the Musrenbang Village. BKPRMI's participation in decision-making is very important, because young people are required to determine development directions and strategies according to the attitudes and culture of the local youth. Participation in decision making is a process in choosing alternatives given by all elements of youth, social institutions and others. Youth participation in decision making in the development plan process, usually carried out through deliberation to reach consensus, aims to choose alternatives in planning development implementation.

The implementation of BKPRMI's participation had a positive but not significant effect on the Musrenbang Village. The success of a development program depends on the participation of the community in participating throughout. According to Koentjaraningrat (1998), states that community participation,

especially rural communities in development actually involves two types which are different in principle, namely: a). Participation in joint activities in special development projects. In the first type, rural communities are invited, ordered to do work that is physical in nature. If the community participates based on their belief that the project will be beneficial to them, then they will participate with enthusiasm and spontaneity, without expecting high wages. Conversely, if they are only governed and forced by their superiors to donate their labor or property to the project, they will not participate in the spirit earlier, and b). Participation as an individual outside of joint activities in development. In this type of participation there are no specific, but joint, joint activity projects including development projects, not physical in nature and do not require orders or coercion from their superiors, but based on their own volition.

Assessing program results from BKPRMI participation has a positive but not significant effect on the Musrenbang Village. Community participation in development planning is believed by many to have become a key word in the development of development in the current era of regional autonomy. Development that involves community participation has failed to create justice and public welfare. Participation is a bridge between the government as the holder of power, authority and policy with the people who have the civil, political and socio-economic rights of the community. With community participation, the bargaining position of the people in the eyes of the government is increasing, the community is not always dictated and dominated by the government in fulfilling their needs or decisions in environmental development but always involved in decision making and implementation.

The concept of participation is a broad, and important concept, because one indicator of the success of a development is the participation of young people who receive

the program. Someone who participates actually experiences his involvement or his ego which is more than just involvement in work or duty. The involvement of a person in certain activities shows that his feelings pertain to or agree to implement and his mind supports that someone needs to carry out these activities. The active participation of youth in development programs requires awareness of the youth of the same interests and interests, which can be realized with an awareness strategy. For the success of the program, young people are required to be involved not only in the cognitive and practical aspects, but also emotional involvement in the program.

The results showed that members of the BKPRMI Lubuk Pakam sub-district had participated but not yet to the maximum, this was seen from the insignificant influence of BKPRMI's participation in the implementation of development programs and assessing program results. According to Juliantara (2002) the substance of participation is the work of a government system where no policy is taken without the consent of the community, while the basic direction to be developed is the empowerment process, further said that the objectives of developing participation are: 1) that participation will allow the community independently (autonomously) organizes itself, and thus will make it easier for the community to face difficult situations, and be able to reject various adverse trends; 2) the status of participation is not only a concrete mirror of the opportunities for expressing aspirations and ways to fight for it, but more importantly that participation becomes a kind of generation for not being ignored by the interests of society; 3) that the problems in the dynamics of development will be overcome by community participation. From this basis, it can be concluded that youth participation in the implementation of government policies will be seen from the behavior of supporting and carrying out the activities of development programs implemented.

In deciding someone to do something in participating there is a need for behavior from the young man himself. Every individual in behavior is very determined by very complex factors such as physiological factors such as the state and physical and mental abilities of a person, psychological factors such as perception, attitude, personality, intelligence, motivation, environmental factors such as family, culture, label attached to someone like social status, self-esteem, education level, and so on.

CONCLUSION

Factors that influence the participation of members of the Indonesian Mosque Youth Youth Communication Board (BKPRMI) in the Musrenbang Village, namely education, employment, understanding, and regulations simultaneously have a significant effect. Partially the education and understanding variables have a positive and significant effect on the participation of BKPRMI members, while the work and regulatory variables have a positive but not significant effect on the participation of BKPRMI members. Variable participation of members of the Indonesian Mosque Youth Youth Communication Board (BKPRMI) which includes decision making, implementation, receiving benefits, and evaluating the results of the program simultaneously have a positive and significant effect on the Musrenbang Village. Partially the decision-making variables and receiving benefits have a positive and significant effect on the Musrenbang Village, while the implementation variables and assessing program results have a positive but not

significant effect on the Musrenbang Village.

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